

The Relationship Between Dysmenorrhea Pain and Learning Activities in Nursing Students

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ABSTRACT: Dysmenorrhea is pain felt in the lower abdomen during menstruation due to an imbalance of prostaglandin hormones. Learning activities are student activities in the learning process, both physical activities and psychological activities. One factor that can interfere with learning activities is the level of dysmenorrhea pain. Learning requires a healthy physique, because it will affect body tissues so that learning activities are also good, while physical pain will cause fatigue, lack of enthusiasm, dizziness, etc. WHO (World Health Organization) says the incidence of dysmenorrhea is 1,769,425 people, almost (90%) women experience dysmenorrhea. The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship between dysmenorrhea pain levels and learning activities in female nursing students at the Immanuel Health Institute. The study was conducted in 2023 using a quantitative approach. The design of this study was Cross sectional with a population of 256 students and a sample of 68 female students using proportional stratified random sampling technique. The results of the analysis found that more than half (73.5%) of female students had their learning activities disrupted and obtained a significant P-value of $0.02 < 0.05$ which means there is a relationship between the level of dysmenorrhea pain and learning activities at the Immanuel Health Institute. Suggestions in this study are the need for relaxation techniques to divert pain for students with various techniques such as deep breathing, listening to music and other non-pharmacological therapies.

KEYWORDS: dysmenorrhea, learning activity.

INTRODUCTION

One disorder that often occurs in women is dysmenorrhea. they exhibit cramp-like, dull, throbbing pain which usually originates from the lower abdomen, and occurs just before and/or during menstruation. Dysmenorrhea is pain felt in the lower abdomen during menstruation due to an imbalance in the hormone prostaglandin (Pradini, 2020). Some studies suggest that a milder type of menstrual pain than dysmenorrhea, called normal menstrual cramps, may occur (Grandi, G., Ferrari, S., Xholli, A., Cannoletta, M., Palma, F., Romani, C., ... & Cagnacci, A. (2012)). Dysmenorrhea is divided into 3 levels, namely mild, moderate, severe. Dysmenorrhea can affect daily activities, especially for teenagers, including difficulty concentrating, often not attending lectures, emotional conflicts, tension, anxiety, and disrupting the learning process, feeling uncomfortable, decreased activity in the learning process, sleeping soundly (Proverawati, 2020). WHO (World Health Organization) states that the incidence of dysmenorrhea is 1,769,425 people, almost (90%) of women experience dysmenorrhea. A student is someone who is in the process of gaining knowledge and studying in one form of higher education which includes universities, institutes, high schools and academics. Learning activities are student activities in the learning process, both physical activities and psychological activities. Studying requires a healthy physique, because it will affect body tissues so that learning activities are also good, while physical pain will cause fatigue, lack of enthusiasm, easy dizziness, etc. (Anggreini Wakyu Prastika, 2019).

Learning activities can be disrupted, less enthusiastic, and concentration decreases because someone experiences menstrual pain (dysmenorrhea) so that the material presented during learning cannot be received well (Dewi, 2019).

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a quantitative research design with cross sectional techniques. The research location is at the Immanuel Health Institute and was carried out in April-August 2023 with a population of 256 students and up to 68 female students using a sampling technique. proportionate stratified random sampling, data collection techniques using questionnaires, and conducting univariate and bivariate analysis.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Dysmenorrhea Pain Level

Table 1. Level of dysmenorrhea pain

Characteristics	Frequency	%
Light	5	7.4
Currently	42	61.8
Heavy	21	30.9
Total	68	100.0

Based on table 1 of 68 female students, it can be explained that the distribution of respondents is more than half of female students who experience moderate pain during menstruation, namely the frequency of 42 (61.8%) female students.

Learning activity

Table 2. Learning activities

Category	Frequency	%
Disturbed	50	73.5
Not disturbed	18	26.5
Total	68	100.0

Based on table 2, more than half of 50 (73.5%) had their learning activities disrupted.

Relationship between dysmenorrhea pain levels and learning activities

Table 3. Relationship between dysmenorrhea pain levels and learning activities

Dysmenorrhea Pain Level	Learning activity			P Value
	Disturbed	Undisturbed	Total	
Light	4	1	5	0.02
Currently	29	13	42	
Heavy	17	4	21	
Total	50	18	68	

Based on the results carried out in the Chi-Square test, the value or p value obtained is 0.02. $p < 0.05$ means H_0 is rejected or H_a is accepted, which means that there is a significant relationship between the level of dysmenorrhea pain and the learning activities of female students.

DISCUSSION

This research is in line with research by Astrida (2012) which divides dysmenorrhoea into three levels of severity, namely mild dysmenorrhoea, which is pain that is felt to last for a moment or is still tolerable, does not require treatment and does not interfere with daily activities, moderate dysmenorrhoea, namely starting to respond to the pain by pressing. painful parts, and severe dysmenorrhoea which is unbearable pain and the pain spreads to the waist or other parts of the body accompanied by symptoms of dizziness, headache, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea and nausea. This research is also in line with Dewi's (2021) research with the title "The Relationship between Anxiety Levels and Dysmenorrhea and Student Learning Concentration". The result was that more than half (57.2%) of female students experienced moderate pain. This agrees with Astrida (2012) who divides dysmenorrhea into 3 levels, namely mild dysmenorrhea, which is pain that is felt to last for a moment or is still tolerable, does not require treatment and does not interfere with daily activities, moderate dysmenorrhea, namely starting to respond to the pain by pressing on the affected part. pain, and severe dysmenorrhea which is unbearable pain and the pain spreads to the waist or other parts of the body accompanied by symptoms of dizziness, headache, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea and feeling depressed.

Based on the results of research conducted on 68 female students, it shows that more than half (73.5%) of female students had their learning activities disrupted. This research is in line with Fitri Hironima N, 2020 The research results show that there is significant relationship between dysmenorrhea and learning activities ($0.000 < 0.05$) The conclusion of this research is that there is an influence of menstrual disorders on learning activities for DIII Midwifery students. The large number of female students who experience menstrual pain makes it difficult for students to concentrate in their learning process due to discomfort. This causes some female students' achievements to decline and they often do not participate in class learning (Alimudin, 2017).

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The relationship between dysmenorrhea pain levels and learning activities

Based on the results of the Chi-Square test, it shows that $p < 0.05$ ($p = 0.02$) means that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, so it can be said that there is a relationship between the level of dysmenorrhea pain and learning activities in female students. This research is in line with Putri's 2021 research, there is a relationship between dysmenorrhea and learning activities at SMK N 1 Tabanan. Other research Prandini, 2020 in The results of the statistical test show that the P value is 0.000, which means there is a relationship between menstrual pain and learning activities among female students in the Nursing Science study program.

The learning process requires concentration on learning. Concentration for each person is the process of focusing the mind on a particular object. This means that the work or actions we do are carried out seriously by focusing all our five senses, smell, sight, hearing and mind (Fahyuni & Istikomah, 2014).

Learning activities can be disrupted, lack of enthusiasm, and concentration decreases because someone experiences menstrual pain (dysmenorrhea) so that the material presented during learning cannot be received well (Dewi, 2019). The learning process requires concentration on learning. Without concentration on learning, actual learning events do not exist or do not take place (Pujiana & Lestari, 2017). Concentration for each person is the process of focusing the mind on a particular object. This means that the work or actions we do are carried out seriously by focusing all our five senses, smell, sight, hearing and mind (Fahyuni & Istikomah, 2014). Learning activities can be disrupted, lack of enthusiasm, and concentration decreases because someone experiences menstrual pain (dysmenorrhea) so that the material presented during learning cannot be received well (Dewi, 2019).

CONCLUSION

There is a relationship between the level of dysmenorrhea pain and learning activities in female students

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